

CULTURE AND HERITAGE

THE ROLE OF BOATS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RIVER CULTURE — INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE IN THE MEKONG DELTA, VIETNAM

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ABSTRACT

Background: Nowadays, while preserving and promoting core identity values, globalization, and integration are inevitable trends of sustainable development. In the context of modernization in recent years, boats in the Mekong Delta, although decreasing in number, still play an essential role in shaping the culture of the South. Boats are present in most activities, from beliefs and religions to social life, so they have become a typical symbol of the residents here. **Methods:** In this study, we used qualitative research methods to analyze the richness and diversity in shape and size and the flexibility in the function of boats in the floating market culture in the Mekong Delta. Data were collected by analyzing documents, artifacts, historical images, and field surveys. **Results:** The research results indicate that the Mekong Delta's historical conditions, geographical features, and complex river systems have formed the habit of using boats with many methods and roles from social life, festivals, and spirituality..., creating a diversity of styles and unique forms boats, market meetings on the river, creating a vivid cultural picture of the Mekong Delta. **Conclusion:** To focus on the research objective of the diversity and role of boats, the author could not fully describe the unique processes and stages of their development in detail but clarified the value of boats in social life and sustainability over time. Boats serve the needs of transporting goods and people and carry the riverside community's customs, habits, and distinctive cultural features. However, urbanization has increasingly narrowed the area of floating markets, reducing the number of boats and affecting some characteristics of their types, designs, and functions. This has deeply affected the typical values of the floating market culture. **Recommendation:** Therefore, the proposed study recommends that authorities and businesses, especially in the tourism sector, pay attention and implement appropriate policies to preserve and maintain boats and the unique intangible culture of the river region.

KEY WORDS

Mekong Delta Boats, Floating Market Culture, Social Life of Boats, Cultural Preservation.

INTRODUCTION

The Mekong Delta is a geographical area with a dense river network, which is the premise for using boats. This natural condition has connected the development of trade from one province to another, from one country to another through trade activities, waterway transport, and the development of tourism culture. The river conditions with many river sections have created key floating market areas for trade. This creates a unique feature of the Mekong Delta, which is the river culture in the floating market, creating conditions for boats to develop more richly and diversely.

For the Mekong Delta and Vietnam, “floating market culture” is an important characteristic that creates a unique feature in the socio-economic development and tourism services or waterway transport associated with boats. The influence and essential role of ships in this unique culture was affirmed when the “floating market culture” was recognized by the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism of Vietnam as a national intangible cultural heritage on March 10, 2016, making an essential contribution to connecting the Mekong Delta with other localities as well as internationally. Traditional boats are vital for merchants who live near the water, particularly river passenger boats, which are essential transportation links in specific regions (Hasanudin, Dwi Saputra, & Nugroho Yulianto, 2025). Boats have existed in Vietnam for centuries. Through the diversity of forms and functions of vessels, it can be seen that their social life plays a vital role in the development of river culture (Whelan, 2016). These unique values need to be preserved and promoted in the right direction so that the Mekong Delta and Vietnam can develop sustainably in the process of integration with the world (Sutton & Anderson, 2020).

Boats have existed in Vietnam for centuries. Through the diversity of forms and functions of vessels, it can be seen that their social life plays a vital role in the development of river culture (Whelan, 2016; Pham et al., 2010). These unique values need to be preserved and promoted in the right direction so that the Mekong Delta and Vietnam can develop sustainably in the process of integration with the world (Sutton & Anderson, 2020). This creates a unique feature of the Mekong Delta, which is the river culture in the floating market, creating conditions for boats to develop more richly and diversely (Nhân & Thông, 2016; Huỳnh, 2011). Vietnam’s terrain also has a long coastline and a network of rivers, which facilitated the use of boats and watercraft from a very early age (Nguyễn, 2019). In Vietnam, the shipbuilding industry developed strongly from the

Nguyen Dynasty (1802–1945) and lasted until the end of King Tu Duc’s reign. During this period, Vietnamese boats were famous for their quantity and throughout Asia. The long-standing presence of vessels in Vietnam also created conditions for river culture to become unique (Nguyễn, 2019).

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It can be seen that the natural conditions and the long history of using boats have created a river culture, specifically a floating market culture with the inevitable presence of boats. Boats participate in this process with many roles, such as water transport and transporting people and goods; boats are also a means of fishing, aquaculture, and especially human housing, which people respect and are always present in festival activities or extraordinary beliefs. With diverse functions from life and society to spirituality, boats in the Mekong Delta have become typical cultural symbols of river residents with many unique and varied forms, sizes, and types.

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connecting the Mekong Delta with other localities as well as internationally. Traditional boats are vital for merchants who live near the water, particularly river passenger boats, which are essential transportation links in specific regions (Pham et al., 2010). The dense concentration and diversity of boats have formed many bustling floating markets along the Mekong River. All these factors have created a closely linked system of river culture, floating markets, and boats, promoting the strong development in all aspects of the Southern region of Vietnam.

Playing an essential role in forming Southern culture, specifically floating market culture, Ghe gradually became a symbol of Southern residents in most activities, from religion and beliefs to daily life. Over time, with population growth, urban areas gradually changed as markets and the residential regions expanded on land. To cope with this urbanization process, markets, supermarkets, and other forms of industrial production on land have also developed continuously. Since then, floating markets and boats have gradually narrowed and significantly reduced in number. Adapting to the needs of use in the new context, in some conditions and exceptional cases, such as the tourism industry, has led to changes in the function, style, and size of many boats. Although units and businesses have been interested in using boats or promoting floating market culture, the effectiveness and connection between these efforts are not yet synchronous and tight. Some boats have been misused, causing damage or reducing the unique integrity of the culture.

Therefore, it is necessary to have the proper orientation to ensure the aesthetic integrity and the inherent unique nature of the boat from shape to decoration or function. This contributes to creating sustainable development values for the area. The boat and the social life of the boat in the river culture need to be cared for, preserved, oriented, and developed appropriately. It is a multi-faceted connection from history, culture, application... to create value in the social life of an object (Appadurai, 1988). Tourism, learning about traditions, and experiencing indigenous culture have grown in recent years. This trend creates sustainable development for regions not only in the tourism industry but also in the economy, culture, and society if we know how to exploit and appropriately apply the unique cultural values of boats.

From the above reasons, it can be seen that boats are artifacts that reflect and represent the society and culture of the people of the Mekong Delta,

Vietnam, located in the river region, creating a distinct culture and becoming a vibrant river cultural landscape, creating an essential foundation for sustainable development for the area. This study was conducted with the theme "The role of boats in the development of river culture - intangible cultural heritage in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam" to serve that purpose.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Over time, with population growth, urban areas gradually changed as markets and the residential regions expanded on land. To cope with this urbanization process, markets, supermarkets, and other forms of industrial production on land have also developed continuously. Since then, floating markets and boats have gradually narrowed and significantly reduced in number. Adapting to the needs of use in the new context, in some conditions and exceptional cases, such as the tourism industry, has led to changes in the function, style, and size of many boats (Pham et al., 2010). Although units and businesses have been interested in using boats or promoting a floating market culture, the effectiveness and connection between these efforts are not yet synchronous and tight. Some boats have been misused, causing damage or reducing the unique integrity of the culture (Whelan, 2016).

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This study is essential because it uses qualitative methods. This study aims to achieve three main objectives: (1) Study the natural conditions, river landscape, and floating market culture, as well as

show the long-standing tradition of using boats in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam. (2) Study the river culture through typical floating markets in the Mekong Delta; (3) Analyze the role of boats in social and spiritual life. The diversity of forms and flexibility of functions show the critical role of boats in forming intangible cultural identity values. It aims to promote sustainable development and integrate and preserve indigenous river culture. Qualitative research method, field work: data collection by interviewing key informants, general interviews, general observations, and participant observation. File trip most provinces and cities in the Mekong Delta region, such as Ben Tre, Can Tho, Long An, Tien Giang, Vinh Long, Hau Giang, Soc Trang, and An Giang, were surveyed through fieldwork. This includes surveys of areas with floating markets and typical boat-building workshops of each region, such as the Cai Rang floating market, Nga Bay floating market, Cai Be floating market, and other boat-building workshops.

Ethnography method: direct observation and interviews to study the culture and lifestyle of groups of people using boats such as tourists, boat owners, boat-building workshop owners, experienced boat builders and repairers ... to better understand boats, their characteristic structures, shapes, materials ... through direct measurements at boat-building workshops. Along with that is learning about the methods and culture of use when directly participating in making, using, exchanging, and chatting with owners, boat workshop owners, and long-time boat builders. Directly visiting and experiencing floating markets, yachts, ferries, ships... to collect detailed and rich data, better understand the culture of rivers.

Data Collection and Document Analysis

The research process was carried out meticulously. Historical documents accompanied an initial literature review on geographical conditions, history, culture, and the use of boats and floating markets in the Mekong Delta.

Population and Groups

The researcher himself visited the floating market, contacted the residents of the river area, and directly experienced and lived with the local merchants, who used boats from many perspectives and roles.

People Who know or Use Directly (Insiders)

- Merchants, boat owners: use boats every day and live closely with the social life of boats.
- Boat builders: interviewing boat owners who are currently primary.

- Experts: experts in the field of tourism culture.

Regular Informal

- Government officials: interviewing and synthesizing documents, deciding that Cai Rang Floating Market is a national intangible cultural heritage.
- Tourists: interviewing tourists
- Traders: (merchants) interview merchants who are descendants of the previous generation of merchants about the history of their boats, their use, and maintenance costs. Artisans and artists create works of literature, art, and films that are interested in the traditional cultural beauty of boats.

Instrumentation

Instruments or tools for Data Collection: Interview form, field work note book, audio recorder, camera and video, etc

Data Collection

Field working: to collect the data by key informant interview, general interview, general observation and participant observation, etc.

Documentary data: to collect the information from books, documents, images, media, including in the Internet, etc.

Data Analysis

This study is the qualitative methodology, and the writing method used is descriptive analysis combined with pictures and diagrams. After collecting data by field survey and literature review, I divided the data into groups:

Data collection was conducted throughout the study. The data is classified into two groups:

Group 1: Data on boats, culture, historical of floating markets in South Vietnam, Mekong Delta, Can Tho: Includes books, newspapers, magazines, research articles, scholars related to boats and river culture of South Vietnam.

Group 2: Data on boat building techniques, types of boats, and parameters. Includes video, interview photos, and notes.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical practices were followed throughout the research. All participants interviewed and involved in the fieldwork gave their informed consent. Using the interview and narrative method, the close relationship between boats and social life was highlighted, highlighting river culture as an intangible cultural heritage that needs to be preserved and developed sustainably in Vietnam's new context.

Figure 1: Research Diagram.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Research on Natural Conditions, River Landscape, and Floating Market Culture shows the Long-standing Tradition of using Boats in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

Boats are symbols in the visual culture as well as the religious culture of many civilizations, including Asia. (Ballard et al., 2004; Marr & Milner, 1986). The social life of cultural values embedded in boats reflects the deep connection between material culture and intangible heritage (Agha, 2003).

Diverse Forms, Flexible Functional Applications Social Perspective

From a historical and political perspective, boats have been integral to Vietnamese life since ancient times (Adams, 2001; Son, 2022). They have been continuously developed and newly built to serve various activities, ranging from daily life and commerce to politics. Boats were strongly developed and reflected in the boatbuilding industry, especially during the Nguyen Dynasty—the history of the Dang Trong and Dang Ngoai wars (Piétri, 2015; Son, 2022). The Southern/Southwestern region belongs to Dang Trong. In the 17th and 17th centuries, Dang Trong achieved outstanding achievements; the Nguyen lords had a powerful fleet of ships, ensuring commercial transportation needs, notably naval ships. 1671 Rabbi Benige Vachet arrives in the

description of boats (p23-24 marine shipbuilding).

Using warships for the navy was very important during the Tay Son War. The South is a land of rivers and canals, and transportation is mainly by boat. The book *Dai Nam Nhat Thong Chi* describes the terrain of Vinh Long County as follows: “In the sea, in the river, in the lake, in the land, it seems like the moon and stars are scattered, without boats, it is impossible to travel, so there are many people here. Know how to row. The book *Gia Dinh Thanh Thong Chi* by Trinh Hoai Duc (1765-1825) writes: “There are boats everywhere in Gia Dinh. Boats are crowded on the river, going back and forth day and night”; Tran Vinh Thanh (present-day Can Tho) has a rough terrain, rivers, and rivers circulate intermingled, and without the help of boats, it is impossible to travel. With such terrain, using boats is inevitable. From the issue of military strategy, Lord Nguyen focused on developing the shipbuilding industry with diverse forms and functions. (The Tay Son Navy has a substantial fleet of warships, newly built with high technology, making Westerners admire. Since 1796, Nguyen Anh has promoted boat building at a breakneck pace, “each ship was built in only three months, with 1,200 warships under Nguyen Anh’s command.” In addition to serving domestic needs, Nguyen Anh also built boats for Thailand due to the connection between Nguyen Anh and Thailand (Siam) in the fight against the Tay Son.

Long Xuyen 10 ships, Kien Giang 3, Tran Giang 5, Phu Quoc 8. These boats were completed in 1791 and transferred to Thailand (Siam) to exchange weapons to equip the war against the Tay Son. To serve this purpose, many boat factories were established along the river. The first factory area was located east of Gia Dinh citadel, along the Tan Binh River (Saigon River) to the banks of the Binh Tri-River (Thi Nghe Canal), established in 1790. The second factory is located on the bank of Long Ho River, Vinh Thanh town. The third workshop is Trang Thuyen Tu, located on the Tam Giang Nha Be River (HCMC) banks.

Technically, warships are often built in the European style, while private merchant ships or transport boats are often built in the style of vessels from the Central region (VN). Gourd boats have become a popular type of boat in the South. The technique of dividing compartments has improved. If one container absorbs water, it does not affect the remaining compartments. By the end of the 17th century, many significant advances and developments had occurred. Boats are present in every resident’s daily life and contribute to forming living habits, behavior, understanding, and experience in dealing with nature, rivers, and landscapes. Forming a beautiful,

long-standing river culture, people live in harmony with nature.

Since 1722, the Qing Dynasty (1644-1911) in China has encouraged rice trade between Southeast Asian countries and China. Rice is a bulky commodity with high transportation costs, so it could be more profitable. Therefore, traders need to build boats in Southeast Asia or Vietnam. In 1747, Chinese merchants came to Vietnam and Thailand to hire boatbuilders to ship to China.

The Mekong Delta and Siam (Thailand) are key rice production centers in Southeast Asia (XVII-XIX), where there are excellent and abundant sources of wood. Many Spanish merchants regularly came to Dan Trong. These policies have caused the Mekong Delta. They were becoming a bustling place in Asia in the 18th century. Chinese traders also recruited workers from Vietnam to China to build boats for them. The cultural economy develops very strongly and attracts neighboring countries. Ships are built everywhere to serve this pace. That's why the factories are spread throughout the South, from Dong Nai, Saigon, Rach Gia, and Ha Tien. Spain, Portugal, China, Thailand... gathered in Vietnam.

Wherever the river expands, cultural and economic life develops. During the reign of Lord Nguyen (1802) (3,190 units listed) In his memoir *A Voyage to Cochin China*, John White, a US Navy lieutenant who arrived in Saigon in 1819, highly appreciated and admired the boats in Vietnam during this period: "About 50 boats. The longitudinal sail is built partly in the European style while the bow combines European and Annamese designs." And also commented that one must be talented in water to build such good ships. Policy to promote the building of ships and boats to take advantage of the terrain, consolidate the installation and use of vessels to serve activities adapted to the benefits of rivers, and serve national defense and navigation.

Minh Mang Dynasty (1820-1841) The state promoted boat building in the capital, Hue, focusing on increasing the number of boats and learning Western techniques. He developed the invention of the steam engine. Identify style. The role of vessel and river culture in life and trade. Dynasty Tu Duc (1848-1883) learned shipbuilding techniques from the British. Vinh Long and An Giang, the king, sent workers to Gia Dinh to learn casting in French workshops. * National History Shop of the Nguyen Dynasty, Dai Nam Thuc Luc, volume XXXI, Hanoi Social Sciences Publishing House, 1975, p.20. After the 1862 Nham Tuat Peace Treaty, the Nguyen Dynasty ceded three provinces in the Southeast region (Bien Hoa, Gia Dinh, Dinh Tuong) to France.

The Nguyen Dynasty regulated boat lifespans and divided them into nine types of boats (p.60 and 66.) More than 25 different types of vessels were listed. The royal ships were also named and decorated with engravings according to their positions. The factories of the Nguyen court are rich in types, designs, sizes, quantities, etc., meeting daily needs, transportation needs, equipping the government apparatus, and ensuring national security—room and transporting grain goods. Vietnamese boats developed an extensive, technical, valuable life and waterway transportation network thanks to the Nguyen Dynasty's priority policy, the Tay Son Dynasty, and the Nguyen Dynasty kings, especially Gia Long and Minh Mang (Son, 2022).

The diversity of boats also shows the variety of people's activities during this period, which took place on a vast scale (Kanagawa, Cross, & Markus, 2001; Zheng et al., 2023). As time passed, the used ships entered the repair phase and focused on replacing them with new materials such as metal, cast iron, and steel. At the end of the Tu Duc Dynasty, boat building stopped. (Difficulty competing with imperialist countries and the influence of social exploitation when France and other countries are dividing five years into seven to colonize Indochina countries and even Vietnam.

Research on River Culture through the form of Typical Floating Markets of the Mekong Delta

Typical culture is formed by using boats to geographical features covered by rivers (Adams, 2001; Ballard et al., 2004; Marr & Milner, 1986). The view that waterways are a museum of rivers that needs to be expanded and developed for in-depth tourism is noteworthy (Wantzen, 2023). In the south of Vietnam, many floating markets are formed with unique cultural features (Kanagawa et al., 2001; Urry & Larsen, 2011; Zheng et al., 2023). Wherever the river goes, boats go there. Boats also play an essential role in the lives of coastal residents (Agha, 2003; Appadurai, 1988), but with different cultures and geographical features, the shape and way of use are also different. Suppose the Amzone River's wild beauty and majestic flow is likened to a "fresh water sea". In that case, the journey of boats with the function of tourism also has its color to explore the fascinating culture of South America. Meanwhile, the mysterious Nile River has a relatively gentle flow, occasionally with large floods, but it is still Egypt's primary source of life. It is mainly developed for tourism with sailboats or "hotel ships" also exploited for tourism. Although both of these places also have boats as a typical means of transport, most of them currently serve the purpose

of tourism services; there is no floating market similar to other countries in the same Asian region, such as Thailand or Indonesia. Damnoen Saduak Floating Market in Thailand stands out with its river culture for tourism when the river flows through residential areas, where the bustling activities of buying and selling typical products for tourists are concentrated. Lok Baintan Floating Market (Indonesia) is the first floating market in South Kalimantan. This market has existed for centuries and is considered one of Southeast Asia’s most authentic floating markets, with more than 90% of the vendors being women. Boats from smaller river branches also gather on the Martapura River from sunrise; the boats gather to form a floating market about 2-3 km long. Brightly painted canoes, motorized wooden boats known locally as *klotok*, brightly dressed vendors, and fruit and vegetables add an even more vibrant colour.

In the Mekong Delta, most families own and use boats as a means of transportation for travel and daily activities. The terrain with many river branches often converging in one area will have boats that can easily trade and exchange goods, from agricultural products to seafood or all items that can be conveniently traded. Even when France entered Vietnam in the 19th-20th century, they recognized this geographical advantage and dug more canals to serve the exploitation of the colony more conveniently. A series of canals were born in the Southern region during this period, contributing to the development of waterway traffic. Floating markets were formed naturally according to the living habits of residents. They were often located at the intersections of rivers or branches of rivers and were very bustling. Boats at that time were both means of serving military and political affairs. Boats specializing in commercial transport of goods were everywhere to transport goods and trade from many regions in the South at that time. Goods and

commodities include ceramics from Dong Nai, Song Be, and Ho Chi Minh provinces to the West and agricultural and aquatic products from the Western provinces to Saigon. From then on, the river culture, “Floating market culture” on the wharf and under the boat, was always bustling. Like the roads on land, floating markets were formed everywhere along the flow and gathering areas between the river branches. Especially in the Southwest—the Mekong Delta, many bustling floating markets are still operating today.

There are more than six large floating markets in the South, of which Cai Rang Floating Market is one of the most typical floating markets (Son, 2016). According to those who have lived and traded directly in the floating market since its heyday until now, the Cai Rang floating market is more than 10km long; boats and ships are bustling from 3-4 am, and large boats from Saigon come to deliver goods or buy agricultural products, traders bargain busily everywhere, agricultural fruits are mainly sold by boat, rarely sold by kg. Usually, large boat owners from Saigon can buy one type of agricultural product, such as oranges, tangerines, grapefruits, or pineapples... from many small boats and gather them to transfer to the large Ghe Bau with a volume of several tons or more. Around 6-7 am, the market is less crowded, and large boats begin their journey to transport agricultural products to Saigon and other provinces.

Cai Rang Floating Market— Can Tho

Cai Rang floating market is located downstream of the Can Tho River, about 600m from the Cai Rang bridge. It has a reasonably large water surface area, convenient for floating market activities: the average width of the river is 100-120m, and the length of the river is about 1300-1500m. The relatively large water surface area is located in the Cai Rang district, with about 300-400 boats meeting at the market daily.

Figure 2: Cai Rang Floating Market – Can Tho Map (The map shows Cai Rang Floating Market on a branch of the Hau River flowing through Cai Rang District, Can Tho City, about 6 km from the center. It is located at the intersection of the main river branches, creating conditions for boats to gather.)

Figure 3: Image of Activities at Cai Rang Floating Market (Bustling trading activities on boats at Cai Rang floating market. Tourists are enjoying local specialties right on the boat.)

The attraction of the Cai Rang floating market for tourists is to preserve and promote the characteristics of the river region and the freshness of the goods here, to see the sincerity, simplicity, and rare hospitality of the people of the river region in general. The floating market is an attractive tourist destination that tourists, especially foreign tourists, love to explore and experience, not only preserving the cultural beauty of the river region today (Huynh, 2011; Urry & Larsen, 2011).

Cai Rang Floating Market is also an attractive destination with a strong local identity, attracting many domestic and foreign tourists, improving the lives of the heritage community, and contributing to the locality's socio-economic development. Every five boats go in and out. Four boats are carrying foreign tourists at the market. Today, although the road traffic network has been widely developed, the Cai Rang Floating Market is still growing. The market is on the traffic route to the provinces west of Hau River, such as Ca Mau - Rach Gia. At the same time, this place is also close to Hau River, an inter-regional and international waterway. Cai Rang Floating Market is a gathering place for merchants from all over, creating diverse cultural colors on the floating market. Cai Rang Floating Market's artistic space converges many intangible cultural heritage types: social customs, beliefs, folk knowledge, folk performing arts (don ca tai tu) ... and these heritages are still being preserved and passed down. Despite the changes, there is still the potential to maintain and develop. With the unique cultural and economic values of the Cai Rang floating market, Rough Guide (UK)

travel magazine voted it one of the ten most impressive markets in the world, describing it as a unique place with "colorful tropical boats" selling goods. The website "youramazingplaces" also listed the six most beautiful floating markets in Asia, including the floating markets of the Mekong Delta, of which the Cai Rang floating market is a typical example. Cai Rang floating market culture has been recognized as a national intangible cultural heritage by the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism of Vietnam under Decision No. 829/QD-BVHTTDL dated March 10, 2016.

Using bamboo poles (Cay Beo) is a unique form of advertising at the Cai Rang floating market. Agricultural sellers hang their goods on poles on boats to supply them. Goods sold on boats usually specialize in one type of product. In front of each boat, there is typically a pole hanging the kind of goods the boat carries. For example, if the boat specializes in selling sweet potatoes, a few sweet potatoes will be hung on a bamboo pole, and if the boat sells mangoes, a few mangoes will be hung on a bamboo pole to let buyers know that "Sweet potatoes are sold here" or "Mangoes are sold here." Even more remarkable is that there are items that are hung but not for sale (clothes dried by merchants on boats), sold but not hung (food, noodles, pho...), hanging to sell (when wanting to sell a boat, people will hang coconut leaves used for roofing). Cai Rang Floating Market usually opens early, from dawn, and closes around 8 or 9 pm. In the past, people often used three-leaf boats, five-leaf boats, and sampans to go to the floating market.

The market is busiest around 7-8 am. The market does not operate well during the Lunar New Year (the first and second days of the Lunar New Year) and the Doan Ngo Festival (the fifth day of the fifth lunar month). Due to the needs of market-goers, there are not only fruit and agricultural product boats but also many other types of services: pho, hu tieu, coffee, floating shops... Service boats (usually small boats) weave in and out to serve market-goers and tourists.² Nga Bay Floating Market - Hau Giang

Figure 4: Nga Bay Floating Market (The market is located at the intersection of 7 rivers: Cai Con, Mang Ca, Bung Tau, Soc Trang, Xeo Mon, Lai Hieu, Xeo Vong. We can see the main branches of Nga Bay floating market from above, variety of boats gathered at the floating market.)

Nga Bay Floating Market, also known as Phung Hiep Floating Market, was established in 1915 in Nga Bay town. It is one of the most famous and oldest floating markets in the West. The market is about 75km from Hau Giang center and about

35km from Can Tho. Its special feature is that it is located at the intersection of seven rivers. Nga Bay Floating Market, also known as Phung Hiep Floating Market, was once famous for its history of over a hundred years and the busiest trading atmosphere in the Mekong Delta. After ten years of digging canals here, the Nga Bay Floating Market was formed around 1915. The market is located at the intersection of 7 rivers: Cai Con, Mang Ca, Bung Tau, Soc Trang, Xeo Mon, Lai Hieu, and Xeo Vong. Many craft villages have been formed along the river, including boat building, weaving, and farming. With Nga Bay Floating Market, the gathering at seven river branches has become a unique feature that is difficult to blend in and will be a mystery that attracts those who love to travel to the West to explore because each river branch has a unique craft village that is not the same. Nga Bay Floating Market often sells vegetables, household items, handicrafts, southern dishes, and fruits such as rambutan, mangosteen, and durian. In particular, there are also unique "items" such as snakes, geckos, birds, squirrels, turtles...

This is a famous market in Hau Giang province, where the buying and selling activities and exchange of goods of the residents of the Mekong Delta River region take place. Not only that, but it is also a place that attracts many tourists. Each boat sells only one type of fruit or item, and it will be suspended on a high pole called a beo tree to advertise.

Nga Nam Floating Market — Sóc Trang

Figure 6: Nga Nam Floating Market – Sóc Trang (Nga Nam floating market was formed at the confluence of 5 river branches, with many busy boats.)

It is the name of the famous floating market in Nga Nam town, Soc Trang province, located at the intersection of five rivers: Ca Mau, Vinh Quoi,

Long My, Thanh Tri, and Phung Hiep. This is a relatively old and busiest floating market in the Mekong Delta.

Unlike other floating markets, the Nga Nam market starts at 3 a.m.; by 5 a.m., it is more crowded, but at 8 a.m., it begins to close. Visitors will see hanging poles with goods such as cabbage, potatoes, tomatoes, onions, garlic, chili, etc. It can be said that Nga Nam floating market has most of the products of the Mekong Delta, from famous rice varieties of the Western rice granary to vegetables and fruits of the Southern gardens to shrimp, crab, fish, and other typical products of the river region. The market is bustling with the invitations of the boatmen, the floating mobile stalls such as porridge, noodles, fish noodles, coffee... serving the needs of tourists to enjoy. Nga Nam floating market still has attractive rustic countryside features, retains the typical soul of the Western floating market in the Ao Ba Ba, the sweet melodies of the Western folk songs, and the affectionate sayings imbued with the Southern character.⁴ Cai Be Floating Market – Tien Giang. Cai Be floating market is located in Cai Be district, Tien Giang, on Tan Phong island on the vast Tien River bordering the three provinces of Tien Giang, Vinh Long, and Ben Tre. The market is a place to buy and sell goods, a transit station for fruits and products to all regions, and an attractive tourist destination in Tien Giang province. Cai Be Tien Giang is the largest floating market in the Southern region. The market appeared when road traffic was not yet developed, so it was highly bustling because most people had to buy, sell, and exchange right on the river. Not only in the past but also now, this place is still crowded with people visiting and exploring daily.

Figure 7: Cai Be floating Market Represents the Cultural Characteristics of the River Delta Region. (This is the largest floating market in the Southern region and has been bustling since the early 19th century. It is located where the three rivers intersect with Ben Tre and Vinh Long - Along Tan Phong Islet, Tien Giang, in the center of Cai Be town).

Every year, on the occasion of the Doan Ngo Festival, at Cai Be Floating Market in Tien Giang, there is a unique sandbar bathing festival called “Tam Con” (Con: is a small area of land rising above the river surface, and sandbar bathing is the act of bathing around this sandbar area). The festival takes place from around 1:00 p.m. to 4:00 p.m. when the water begins to dry up, revealing the islets. People flock here to bathe so that the whole river will be lively (Anh, 2015).

Unlike regular floating markets that only open in the morning, the Cai Be floating market starts trading from early morning until late at night. When dawn breaks, the floating market is bustling like a small street on the river. Boats selling goods such as pho, hu tieu, vermicelli, groceries, etc., run along the sides of boats and ships, looking lively. Sitting on a drifting boat, enjoying a bowl of hu tieu or a cup of aromatic coffee in the morning is an indescribable experience.⁵ Long Xuyen Floating Market – An Giang.

Figure 8: Long Xuyen Floating Market – An Giang (The Long Xuyen floating market is located on the Hau River, a large branch of the Mekong River. Many boats bustle with buyers and sellers.)

Long Xuyen floating market is smaller than other markets but is a place tourists should visit on their floating market tour to find the simple, peaceful, and pristine features of the people and the rivers here. The market is about 2 km from Long Xuyen City, along one side of the Red Hau River with

heavy alluvium. Long Xuyen Floating Market is located on Hau River, in My Phuoc ward, Long Xuyen City, An Giang province. Because it is not affected by commercialization, this market is more bustling than many other floating markets.

Long Xuyen floating market is most crowded in the morning. The primary goods are vegetables, melons, squash, cabbage, and famous dishes of An Giang, such as fish noodles and pork skin cakes. The people here live and trade all year round on boats, so they consider this their home.

The primary goods here are crops such as vegetables, melons, eggplants, cabbage, squash, and potatoes, as well as famous snacks from An Giang such as fish noodles, rice cakes, pork skin cakes, etc. The remarkable thing is that the goods are bought and sold without any challenges, bargaining, or selling, as said because the floating market here has few tourists visiting; the people are friendly, honest, and unaffected by the commercialization of tourism.

Tra On Floating Market — Vinh Long

Figure 9: Tra On Floating Market – Vinh Long (Various types of boats serving tourists at the Tra On floating market).

Tra On the floating market is the last on the Hau River of Tra On district, Vinh Long province. This

is one of the oldest markets and is also associated with many cultural activities of the people in the area. Tra On floating market is located downstream of Hau River and about 250m from Tra On estuary. This place is a wholesale market because it sells many agricultural products such as taro, sweet potato, cucumber, Tan Thanh orange, Luc Si Thanh durian... Tra On floating market is about 250m from the Tra On estuary. This market is held according to the tide, so when the tide rises, the Tra On floating market gathers many boats to trade, extremely busy on the Hau River, which is more than 300m long. Sometimes, when the tide rises in the early morning, the market attracts hundreds of large and small boats from Vinh Long province and neighboring provinces to trade and exchange goods along with Cu Lao An Binh.

The unique feature of the Tra On floating market is that it gathers according to the tide; the market is crowded in the morning but is more bustling when the tide starts to rise; the higher the tide, the more crowded the boats and ships.

Boats used as Housing: Boats function as mobile homes for merchants. The ship has places to live, rest, and cook. You can even keep pets. The vessel's body is usually divided into an engine area, an area for the boat driver to observe, and a resting area. Most of the boat's body is a large capacity area to transport goods and carry passengers. Depending on the size of each type of boat, the functional areas are arranged for the most convenience. For bathing and washing, use river water.

(a)

(b)

Figure 10: Boats are used as a means of Trading on the River, Even for Buying and Selling Food. Boats are Like Mobile Restaurants (kitchens). (a) A Small Trading Boat with Complete Kitchen Equipment and Cooking Ingredients. (b) The Boat also Serves as a Restaurant on the River, Providing Visitors with an Impressive Dining Experience.

At the floating market, people often buy and sell agricultural products. To make it easier to

observe or attract customers, they have a form of advertising and marketing by using bamboo trees as “cay Beo” to hang the items they sell for easy observation. Hanging pineapples means selling pineapples, and hanging potatoes means selling potatoes. However, there are also unique things that the locals always understand here: “Hanging something to sell that thing (hanging bananas to sell bananas, hanging cabbage to sell cabbage..); hanging this thing but selling something else

(hanging coconut leaves when you want to sell the boat you are using); hanging but not selling (because people live on boats when bathing or drying clothes, they will hang them on the back of the boat, so these clothes are not sold); selling but not being able to hang (boats selling breakfast foods such as vermicelli and noodles cannot hang the food). This is the characteristic of “4 hanging” in the floating market.

Figure 11: Some Large Boats Increase the Usable Area, so they Need to Use many Methods to Carry more. Because the Visibility is Limited, it is Necessary to have Someone at the Bow to Observe. (a) In the Picture is a Giant Boat Carrying Rice Husks. (b) The Back of the Giant Rice Husk Boat.

Some large boats increase their usable area, so they must employ multiple methods to carry more cargo. Because visibility is limited, it is necessary

to have someone at the bow to observe. In the picture, there is a giant boat carrying rice husks.

Figure 12: Another Giant Junk Design with a Different Transport Function would have the Hull of the Boat Fitted as a Living Space.

Figure 13: Scene of Goods and Fruits being Passed Around at the Floating Market.

(a)

(b)

Figure 14: Hanging Goods on the “Beo tree” for Customers to Easily Observe is a Unique form of Marketing in the Floating Market. (a) Usually, whatever is sold is Hung up. (b) Another form of Hanging Goods.

Figure 15: Clothes are Being Hung Out to Dry so this is called “Hanging but not Selling” Because the Boat is like a House to Live in, People will Bathe, Wash, and Dry Clothes on the Ship. These Items are also called “Hanging,” but of Course, they Cannot be Sold Because they are Personal Items.

Figure 16: Hot Foods Like Noodle Soups Cannot be Hung Like Vegetables and Fruits, So they are Called “Sold without Hanging”.

Figure 17: When People want to sell their Boats, They will hang up Roof Leaves. This is Called “Hanging one thing but Selling Another”.

Figure 18: Simulation of the Structure and Function of the Ghe Bau Boat. In the 3D Drawing of PhD Student Tuyen Nguyen. <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ghe-bau-can-tho-20519ec85bba46c2a3fdf903a0d59167>

Through the Diversity of Forms and Flexibility of Functions, Boats' Role in Social and Spiritual Life Demonstrates the Critical Role of Ships in Forming Intangible Cultural Identity Values

With flexible functions, boats become a means of transport for many residents here. Large rivers carry a lot of goods and have large boats; small rivers carry little goods and have small and medium boats (Agha, 2003; Appadurai, 1988). Boats for transporting goods differ from boats for taking passengers across the river; boats for fishing differ from boats for transporting fish, rice, wood, or construction materials. Considering the combination of water, boats and people in relation to the flow of the canal system, the boat's shape is designed to suit the river's water flow characteristics. (Moro et al., 2013). Depending on each function, boats are transformed to suit the application. The boat's shape is designed to suit the river's water flow characteristics (Favacho et al., 2016; Moro et al., 2013; Rhoden & Kaaristo, 2020). In southern Vietnam, most boats

serve the needs of daily life and transportation rather than offshore fishing. Typical boats often have a flat bow and a large, round body (Maia & Said, 2019).

Ferry, passenger ferry (Đò dọc ò ò ngan): Passenger ship, passenger ship (ferry). Wherever rivers and canals go, boats can go there. Boats are used as the primary means of transport. Like today's high-quality buses and coaches, ferries transport people and goods to all districts, provinces, and cities along the rivers. In Can Tho, passenger ships have been in operation since around 1958. The routes, such as Vi Thanh - Bay Ngan to Can Tho, usually run long distances. Next are the Vinh Thuan - Can Tho routes. Can Tho go to Tra On, Cau Quang, Cau Ke, or Tra Cu? Can Tho go to Cai Sau, Bung Binh, Ben Ba, Cai Cui, Cai Dau, Mai Dam... People go to Can Tho to exchange goods, buy and sell agricultural products, and sell fruits at higher prices. On average, from Cai Cui, it takes from 2 am to 6 am to Can Tho if traveling by small boat. At that time, Can Tho was Tay Do - the capital of the Mekong Delta until today.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 19: Boats Carrying Passengers Across the River Means Running Along the Riverbank Called "Do Ngan". Boats are used to Transport Passengers, Small Rivers use Small Boats. (a) "Do doc" Ferry Running Along the Ca Mau Route, Also Known as a Passenger Ship. (b) Boats Run Along the Length of the River Called "Do Doc" (c) Boats are used to Transport Goods and Passengers.

Figure 20: Ferry - a Type of Water Vehicle that Transports Goods and Passengers.

(a)

(b)

Figure 21: Boats are used as means of Transporting Products and Special Goods. (a) Bau Boat is One of the Typical means of Transporting Agricultural Rice Products. (b) Bau Boat is a Typical means of Transporting Tet Flowers.

(a)

(b)

Figure 22: Boat as a means of Business. (a) Boat used as a means of Beverage Business Buying and Selling Regional Specialties by Boat. (b) Beautiful Hand-woven Patterned Mats from one Place are Brought to Another Place for Sale.

(a)

(b)

Figure 23: Boat as a means of Living as a House. (a) Grandma Teaches her Grandchildren on the Boat. (b) Family Meal on the Boat.

Figure 24: Boat used as a means of Trading Food, with Full Kitchen and Typical Dishes.

Rarely is there any property in Vietnam that performs multiple functions, like boats. It is a characteristic that suggests a green economy and a strong national identity.

When boats are very simple and rustic, they convey and carry multiple functions, as seen in Vietnam; they serve as both homes and vessels rather than as real estate. They hold both memories and the promise of the future.

Few assets in Vietnam can perform as many functions as boats. This feature evokes a green

economy and a strong national identity (Kanagawa et al., 2001; Zheng et al., 2023).

When boats are simple and rustic, they represent and perform multiple functions, as seen in Vietnam; they are both a place to live and a means of transportation rather than real estate. They contain both memories and hopes for the future.

- Cultural perspective
- Boats participate in many social activities such as:
- Festivals: Ghe Ngo racing festival and Ghe Ngo racing festival in Soc Trang

Figure 25: Boat Festivals: Ghe Ngo and Ghe Ngo Racing Festival in Soc Trang. (a) Ngo Boat Racing Teams. (b) Preparing to Start. (c) Ngo Boat Racing Practice.

Figure 26: Tong On - Tong Gio Festival.

The origin of this festival comes from the story that there were often many epidemics here. The

people here believed that it was caused by ghosts or the deceased, which was the main reason for

establishing the festival “Tong On - Tong Gio.” The festival “Tong On - Tong Gio” is only held in Can Tho, Vinh Long, and Long An. This festival

is held to pray for peace and luck and prevent epidemics and disasters.

Boats Participating in the Wedding Ceremony

Figure 27: Boats Participating in the Wedding Ceremony. (a) A Beautifully Decorated Boat to Pick Up the Bride. (b) Another Type of Boat Takes the Bride on the Wedding Day. The Rectangular Boat with both Ends Used to Dock was used in the Past to Transport Buffalo and Cows Across the River. This Type of Boat is also called a “Chet.” Nowadays, Small Ferries have been Improved Similarly to Take Passengers Across Small Rivers. In the Picture, A Wedding Procession is Going on the River by “Chet.”

Figure 28: Boats Participate in the Cultural and Artistic Life of the People. (a) Traditional Music on Boats at the Floating Market “Dan Ca Tai Tu”. (b) Boats are also used as Stages for Performing Arts.

Boat Festivals

The Ghe Ngo racing festival, festival boat worshipping customs in the South.

Spiritual Life

Boats and boats are closely associated with the lives of the residents of the Western region due to the interwoven terrain of rivers and canals. Boat traders maintain the custom of worshiping boats according to the customs passed down from ancient times, believing that a sacred being always protects them from having good business and avoiding accidents on rivers, seas, and canals.

Most trading boats and cargo boats worship the “Ba Cau” on the ship and organize boat worshipping each month on the 16th and 29th of

the lunar calendar. Regarding offerings, if land vehicles often worship chickens (symbolizing fast running and jumping), boat worshipping must include ducks (symbolizing swimming and moving smoothly on the river).

The offering tray includes boiled duck with three bowls of porridge, a pot of tea, wine, and cakes; some places also offer a pig’s head, depending on the family’s economy. The offering tray is placed at the bow of the boat. The boat owner burns incense when offering to pray for business, luck, health, etc.

There are “omens” that are not known to be based on any spiritual foundation; for example, the business will be successful if, while moving, a dog is seen wading across the river and in front of

the boat's bow or at night, fireflies appear in the boat's hold; the business will be tricky if a snake or a goose is seen wading across...

The boat-building customs in the Mekong Delta are quite rich, but some similarities exist. To prepare to build a new ship, the owner always worships the first wooden plank, called the "gim lô", by making an offering. On it is a tray of offerings similar to the monthly offering tray of the boat owner, but with a

red cloth symbolizing luck. The "gim lo" wooden plank must be thicker than the following. After completing the boat, the owner must collect the nails hammered into the "gim lo" piece, and the builder must "xâm" other corresponding wooden stakes. Legend believes that if those nails are lost, bad luck will come. The custom of worshipping boats in the Mekong Delta is considered a spiritual and cultural practice, closely associated with traditional folk life for several hundred years.

Figure 29: The Spiritual Custom of Worshipping on Boats. The "Ghe Ngo" Cape is Decorated with Many Colorful Motifs, Symbolizing the Power of the Naga god and Luck.

The spiritual custom of worshipping Ba Cau is indispensable for those who use boats.

Along the length of Vietnam, the West has the most typical terrain. When there are many canals and streams and are pretty close to the sea, due to the unique geographical location, every house will have a boat to travel by. The ship helps them travel on the river, helps them store things, or even live on it. The boat is an indispensable object in the river delta of the West. Since ancient times, our country has always believed in spirituality, with the custom of worshipping ancestors. In addition, before lowering the boat into the water, the people of the West often perform a worship ceremony. The boat worship ceremony is a thank you, praying that the ship will bring peace and luck during use. The boat worship ceremony is a beautiful tradition preserved for generations. Depending on the conditions of each family, there will be different worship ceremonies. The most important thing is the heart of the worshiper. If your heart is sincere, it is still proven without needing a high-class feast. After the boat worshipping ceremony, they will be lowered into the water and tested.

In this spiritual culture, it is easy to see that most

means of transportation are by boat. People in the West often draw a pair of eyes on the boat's bow. With the concept that these are divine eyes that suppress and ward off water monsters in rivers, canals, and streams. Because of the idea that "under the ground, there is a local god, under the river there is a river god." Therefore, people in the West often worship boats and canoes to pray for good luck.

They also pray that the water gods bless and protect the homeowner when they lower the boat into the water and leave the port safely, buy and sell well, and do business smoothly. In addition, the custom of worshipping boats and canoes also has another meaning: remembering the help of "Ba Cau," who helped and punished those who cheated on boats and canoes.

There are many theories about the image of "Ba Cau," but most boat owners often say it is an old woman with two sons who specializes in helping people on the river when they are in trouble. To show their gratitude, the ancient vendors held ceremonies to pray for Ba and her two sons to protect and help them. The image of "Ba Cau" is also used by boaters to remind, warn, and

punish people for wrong actions, words, and bad morals. The ceremony to worship “Ba Cau” on the boat is usually held each month on the 16th and 29th of the lunar calendar. Regarding offerings, if land vehicles often offer chickens (symbolizing lucky jumping activities), then boat offerings must include ducks (symbolizing swimming and smooth movement on the river). The offering tray includes boiled duck with three bowls of porridge, a pot of tea, wine, and cakes, and some places also offer a pig’s head, depending on the family’s economy. The offering tray is placed in front of the boat. When the ceremony starts, the boat owner burns incense to pray for business, luck, health, etc.

The boat offering ritual requires meticulousness and experience in each stage. When preparing to build a new ship, the homeowner always provides the first wooden plank. This is called the “ghim lo” offering. People often include a red cloth on the offering tray. This is the color symbolizing luck. The “ghim lo” wooden plank must always be thicker than the following after completing the boat. The homeowner must collect the nails on the “ghim lo” plank. The boat builder will have to “xam” other corresponding wooden stakes. According to

tradition, lousy luck will occur if those nails are lost.

After the boat worshipping ceremony, the boat owner invites neighboring boats to drink wine and play traditional music. Then they discuss business for the next trip. The boat worshipping ceremony in the Mekong Delta is considered a spiritual and cultural custom in the West. The custom is closely associated with the daily life of the people. This has become a long-standing traditional beauty of the local people.

Another popular boat worshipping ceremony is the “len be” ceremony, which means pulling the boat ashore for repair, renovation, etc. The form is similar to the monthly worshipping ceremony.

There are usually two forms of boat worshipping to start a business trip at the beginning of the year. One is if the boat owner has chosen a good day but for some other reason cannot start the journey; then they will place offerings on the shore then let the boat run back and forth to the place where the offering tray is placed three times, then start the trip on any day they want. The other is that if the trip is immediate, do not do the above actions but start immediately after the worshipping ceremony.

The Spiritual Custom of Worshipping the Water God Every Month

Figure 30: Spiritual Custom of Worship. (a) (b) The Spiritual Custom of Worshipping the Water God Every Day and Month; (c) when Launching a Newly Built Boat.

DISCUSSION

This study aims to propose research topics, promote cooperation, and develop national and international projects to establish specific standards and regulations for the sustainable development of green tourism by studying the social life of boats and the unique river cultural landscape at “Cai Rang Floating Market” in Can Tho, Mekong Delta, Vietnam (Rhoden & Kaaristo, 2020).

Raise awareness, promote the role of departments, branches, sectors, and units related to cultural management, and promote integrated tourism while preserving unique indigenous culture. Encourage people to understand, appreciate, and maintain the nation’s unique cultural and

artistic characteristics, mainly to protect indigenous identity’s intrinsic value fully.

Tourism, learning about traditions, and experiencing indigenous culture have grown in recent years (Johns & Clarke, 2001). Research on boats in the cultural and social identity of the people of the Mekong Delta raises the issue that the Government needs to have policies to support people and occupations related to traditional boats, such as traders, production facilities, artisans, and boat builders. Develop a suitable supply and demand ecosystem in the Mekong Delta region. In addition, the Government also needs to have policies to support the development of river culture models and typical boat models to preserve and promote this typical beauty.

CONCLUSION

Boats have been closely associated with the daily life of Vietnamese people since ancient times when the signs and patterns of boats were engraved on Dong Son bronze drums from the 7th century BC. The process of reclaiming land to the South by the Nguyen Dynasty in 1802, although only over 300 years, with the flexibility and specificity of historical and geographical conditions, the use of boats became increasingly inevitable to develop the socio-cultural economy of the Mekong Delta region, the peak of the shipbuilding industry in Vietnam was trading and exporting boats to countries in the area from the Nguyen Dynasty onwards. Boats, from traditional forms to simpler forms or innovations, are closely associated with the residents here, serving many different functional roles.

In the context of modernization in recent years, boats in the Mekong Delta, although reduced in number, still play an essential role in shaping the culture of the South, especially the floating market culture. Boats have become a typical symbol of the residents here, present in most activities, from beliefs and religions to daily life. The research aims to clarify the value of boats in social life, sustainable over time.

Although urban development has changed the living space when land is exploited deeper inland, residential areas gradually move. Urbanization and social progress are reflected in the formation of new residential areas, the appearance of markets on land or supermarkets, and the gradual dominance of industrial production. Boats are also significantly affected by changes in quantity, function, material, form, and functionality, especially in tourism.

However, the river system is still a prominent feature of the region, expressed through the image of “above the dock, below the boat”, when merchants and traders still use boats to transport goods and agricultural products. The culture of the Southern River region deserves to be preserved and respected. Boats, in general, and gourd boats, in particular, have become beautiful symbols in the hearts of the people of the Mekong Delta, always playing an essential role in all aspects of life, from festivals, tourism, and cultural experiences to art. The image of boats also appears in films, stories by writer Son Nam, and paintings by talented contemporary artists.

In addition, the transformation of the function or shape of the boat also needs to be paid attention to ensure that the social value, historical value, or symbolic image is clearly understood, especially by the younger generation. In addition, it is also necessary to

pay attention to safety factors when using waterway vehicles, preserving the most beautiful images of boats for the next generation and international friends. From the above, it can be affirmed that boats are not only a means of transportation but also an artifact that profoundly reflects the social and cultural life of the people of the Mekong Delta. With the geographical characteristics of rivers, this area has formed a unique culture, creating an attractive river culture picture and carrying many important theoretical values.

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Wooden Barge

PERSPECTIVE OF WOODEN BARGE

TOP SIDE VIEW

Dimensional Drawing of Wooden Barge - 30 Deadweight Tonnage

Perspective Drawing 3D of Wooden Barge - 30 Deadweight Tonnage

Perspective Drawing 3D of Wooden Barge - 30 Deadweight Tonnage

Perspective Drawing 3D of Wooden Barge - 30 Deadweight Tonnage

Perspective Drawing 3D of Wooden Barge - 30 Deadweight Tonnage

Perspective Drawing 3D of Wooden Barge - 70 Deadweight Tonnage

Perspective Drawing 3D of Wooden Barge - 70 Deadweight Tonnage

Perspective Drawing 3D of Wooden Barge - 70 Deadweight Tonnage

Perspective Drawing 3D of Wooden Barge - 70 Deadweight Tonnage